

Trip Advisor Resort Online Reviews in Bali. Content Analysis Based on Big Data

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ABSTRACT: The Trip Advisor online reviews are unstructured information useful for the dynamic interaction in the hospitality industry and accommodation. In any case, there is an absence of examination investigating the online reviews information. This exploration examining the online reviews information from a resort in Bali, Indonesia, from 2019 until 2021 to investigate the insight of the dataset. The cycle begins with examining the word recurrence and expression recurrence content investigation; moreover, the exploratory factor examination was directed to uncover the Aaker brand character from the online reviews dataset. The exploration discoveries show that the hotel has five brand character measurements: sincerity, sophistication, excitement, ruggedness, and competence. The sincerity dimension is the dominant dimension. It is applicable with the word and expression content investigation that uncover the most incessant words and expression identify with the staff execution. Further investigation in an assortment of the hospitality industry is important to work on the cycle to use the Trip Advisor online reviews unstructured dataset.

KEYWORDS- Trip Advisor. Online Reviews, Content Analysis, Big Data, Bali

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology allows each business to create its own brand marketing communication channels via websites and social media, as well as provide remarks that anyone may publish and read online. Generated content refers to the various remarks, photographs, and audio given in the web ecosystem. Statements, photographs, and music provided by internet users, for example, are examples of user-generated content, and the content delivered by the brand is called firm / brand-generated content [1].

The remarks studied in this research were those made by TripAdvisor users. Voluntary users provide feedback on their resort visits. As a result, user-generated material differs from gathering views through structured questions in surveys. [2].

Reviews on TripAdvisor are unstructured data [3]. Reviews can only discuss the qualities or amenities of the resort that the user wishes to express, however survey questions are all the same. It differentiates between organized and unstructured data[4][2].

What is offered inside TripAdvisor for unstructured data is also the preference of users. As a result, there are user preference weights in every review, and it is these preferences. They are critical for academics and marketing executives to comprehend. [5].

Among rivals' varied offers, each entity must create excellence and construct a suitable brand to what the target is about. As a result, knowing what customers are delivering and creating brands that are relevant to consumer demands are critical to winning the present competition. [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study focuses on the use of unstructured datasets and exploratory factor analysis of brand personality.

2.1 Unstructured data

Unstructured data is data with little organization for unit analysis. The structured data consists of data units with specified data points. [6][3]. The structured data from the structured question is an example of the survey questionnaire. TripAdvisor's online reviews are an example of an unstructured dataset with a wide range of data points.

2.2 Brand Personality

The brand personality consists of sincerity, sophistication, excitement, competence, and ruggedness. [7][8]. Sincerity is the dimension that shows the performance of the services to the consumer. Excitement is the dimension relate to the newness of the experience. The sophistication dimension relates to the outstanding experience of the resort. The competence dimension relates to the performance of the services. The ruggedness is the dimension that relates to the natural experience.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This is a qualitative study based on non-structural data gathered from TripAdvisor. The first step is to tabulate each word frequency in the dataset (Table 1). The alternative method is to keep track of how frequently the phrase appears. [9][10][11][12]. The final process is the categorization of words in the dataset into the brand personality dimension of SSERC (Sincerity, Sophistication, Excitement, Ruggedness, Competence)[13][8]. The results of this SSRRC will reveal the brand's personality based on the perceptions expressed by TripAdvisor online reviews dataset. [8]

Table 1. Research Method

Research Methodology	Exploratory study
Type of sampling	Nonstatistical sampling
Sample	2019 - 2021 dataset
Data collection methods	Extraction from user-generated content
Information sources	TripAdvisor online platform
Key contributors	Bali Resort online reviews 2019
Data analysis methods	Word frequency content analysis Phrase frequency content analysis Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis with Brand Personality Dictionary [14]
Study period	2019 - 2021
Source	Based on [14][15]

IV. RESULTS

4.1 Word frequency content analysis

The initial step in the analytical procedure is frequency tabulation. Overall, the frequency tabulation of online reviews concludes that the resort delivers a satisfactory experience since the resort's features match expectations. Furthermore, the resort's employees performed admirably. Visitors gave positive feedback on the staff's performance. (Table2).

Table 2. Word Frequency

No	Words	Words Frequency	No	Words	Words Frequency
1	RESPONDED	933	36	RECOMMEND	187
2	STAFF	915	37	YOGA	160
3	RESORT	676	38	FEEL	157
4		658	39	MORNING	157
5	UBUD	637	40	PERFECT	157
6	POOL	634	41	EXPERIENCE	154
7	HOTEL	572	42	RICE	144
8	APOS	563	43	WONDERFUL	143

9	ROOM	559	44	TOWN	141
10	STAY	521	45	COMFORTABLE	138
11	GREAT	434	46	HOME	137
12	STAYED	400	47	MAKE	137
13	VILLA	381	48	SPACIOUS	137
14	FRIENDLY	364	49	EXCELLENT	135
15	SERVICE	364	50	NIGHT	129
16	BEAUTIFUL	347	51	DELICIOUS	123
17	SHUTTLE	335	52	RELAXING	118
18	PLACE	327	53	PEACEFUL	115
19	BREAKFAST	323	54	LOVED	112
20	AMAZING	320	55	SMALL	111
21	FOOD	314	56	CENTRE	110
22	GOOD	303	57	HIGHLY	110
23	NICE	273	58	BATHROOM	109
24	ROOMS	262	59	DINNER	109
25	DAY	259	60	AMP	108
26	FREE	259	61	AREA	108
27	BALI	238	62	BED	107
28	TIME	238	63	WALK	107
29	NIGHTS	231	64	BALINESE	104
30	SPA	228	65	JUN	103
31	RESTAURANT	226	66	ENJOYED	101
32	HELPFUL	204			
33	LOVELY	202			
34	CLEAN	200			
35	PRIVATE	197			

Further elaboration from tabulating the frequency of words in the resort review dataset from 2019-2021 show that staff words with a total frequency of 915 came in second according to the total frequency most frequently conveyed by datasets.

A total of 634 frequencies of the word "pool" related to the pool are provided by the resort. Furthermore, there is also the noun "room." Both indicate that the pool and room facilities delivered by visitors of the resort are the dominant attributes relevant to the visitor experience.

Another attribute that goes into words with frequencies above 300 is the "service" with a frequency of 364. It can be expected because the resort staff has a good performance, so it gets many reviews from visitors.

In addition, there is the word "shuttle" acquires 335 frequencies, and this indicates the facilities provided by the resort have provided a good experience for visitors. Another attribute included in words with a frequency above 100 is "spacious" with 137. It indicates a positive perception of the stay because of the resort's spacious room size or spaciousness.

Next are some words with a positive sentiment: "stay, great, friendly, beautiful." These words also include the ten words with the most frequency in the observation period of the resort. Therefore, it indicates a positive perception of the experience of staying at the resort, and in this way, it can be estimated that most reviews have positive sentiments.

In addition, there is also about "breakfast," which has 323 frequencies, and "food," with 314 frequencies. This result shows that the breakfast provided by the resort has a good experience from consumers. There are also other positive words in the range of 320 frequency numbers, namely "amazing," "good" with 303, and "nice" with a frequency of 273. It shows that visitors get a pleasant experience while in the resort.

A total of 123 frequencies of the word "delicious" related to food provided by the resort, and this result indicates a positive sentiment that the food provided by the resort has a good experience from consumers.

There are still some other facilities that are delivered such as "spa," "restaurant," and also about "Yoga." Interestingly, some words still in the 200-frequency range indicate the experience of the service provided by the resort. For example, words like "helpful" with a frequency of 204, "lovely" with 202 are words that have a positive sentiment.

Besides, there is the word "clean" with a frequency of 200 that relates to the clean environment in the resort. Another essential point to indicate the satisfaction of resort visitors is the word "recommend," with 187 frequencies indicating that resort visitors recommend to others to stay at the resort.

Another word with positive sentiments appears with a frequency of 157, which is "perfect." That is followed by the word "wonderful" with a frequency of 143 and the word "peaceful" with 115. In addition, there is still a considerable frequency in the dataset that is "beautiful" with a frequency of 347, which further adds to the number of adjectives that have positive sentiments in the Resort review dataset.

Next, there is the word "rice" with a frequency of 114, "relaxing" (118), "comfortable" (138), "enjoyed" (101), "excellent" (135), "loved" with a frequency of 112. This word indicates that the resort has provided exemplary service so that consumers willingly give positive reviews about the resort to be shared with other consumers.

4.2 Phrase frequency content analysis

The following study begins with the phrase finder frequency – a phrase composed of two words that have the same meaning. According to the summary, the resort provided reasonable satisfaction to its tourists and was recommended by reviewers. Furthermore, the resort is inextricably linked to the swimming pool, which is the primary feature of this location. The resort's atmosphere is very pleasant. The environment at the resort also has a nice view, and so many visitors give a positive response about the resort (Table 3).

Table 3. Phrase Frequency

No	Phrase	Phrase Frequency
1	RESORT	140
2	POOL VILLA	126
3	PRIVATE POOL	117
4	FREE SHUTTLE	114
5	RESPONDED JUN	102
6	RESPONDED JUL	95
7	RESPONDED SEP	86
8	RESPONDED AUG	78
9	HIGHLY RECOMMEND	76
10	RESPONDED JAN	75
11	SHUTTLE SERVICE	75
12	RESPONDED DEC	71
13	RESPONDED OCT	69
14	RESPONDED FEB	68
15	RESPONDED APR	65
16	AFTERNOON TEA	63
17	RESPONDED MAR	60
18	RICE FIELDS	60
19	FRIENDLY AND HELPFUL	55

Further elaboration relates to the phrase in the second most frequent phrase is "pool villa" with a frequency of 126, next is "private pool" with a frequency of 117, and "free shuttle" with a frequency of 114.

The results of this phrase indicate that the resort is closely related to the swimming pool. The dominant attribute that is the leading facility provided by the resort is the swimming pool, both intended for all visitors, and in the room, which is a private pool.

In addition, there is a "free shuttle," which is also top of mind of the phrase delivered by visitors of the resort. Therefore, it indicates that the Resort service occupies the top spot that visitors remember.

Another thing relevant to the previous findings is that the phrase "highly recommend" is still in the top 10 most mentioned phrases. It shows that the resort does provide reasonable satisfaction and is recommended once by resort reviewers.

Another exciting thing is drinking tea in the afternoon, "afternoon tea," a tea activity in the afternoon, is conveyed 63 times by reviewers. This afternoon tea activity can be enjoyed by visitors who stay at the resort from 15.00 – 17.00 for free, so this activity provides a pleasant experience for visitors.

"Rice field" is also a phrase delivered 60 times by reviewers; this is because the neighbourhood also has a nice view of rice fields for the eyes to see. Many visitors have responded positively to this.

Furthermore, there is also the phrase "friendly and helpful". The two words that previously also occupy many positions or frequencies turned out to be a unity. It indicates that the staff who helped process the service at the resort did have an emotional closeness as friends and light-handed. Both characters of the nature of the service are in the phrases conveyed by TripAdvisor visitors.

4.3 Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis

The third analytical step involves keeping track of the frequency of five brand personality dimensions: : sincerity, sophistication, excitement, ruggedness, and competence. According to the summary, the resort received a review category with the phrase sincerity in the Resort 2019 – 2020 statistics, and sincerity controls the majority. Furthermore, sophistication is the second most common review category which means consumers perceive the brand as a person who has a class, high position, or glamour.

Table 4. Brand Personality Dimension Frequency

No	Dimension	Dimension Frequency
1	SINCERITY	1546
2	SOPHISTICATION	772
3	EXCITEMENT	275
4	RUGGEDNESS	166
5	COMPETENCE	152

The many characters of this brand may be deduced from an examination of the online reviews on TripAdvisor. By classifying the phrases that fit into each component of brand personality, Provalis software may be used. Mapping the resort's dominating dimensions is possible because to Software Provalis' computational capabilities (Table 4).

Building the dependability of the research technique with resort review data may be accomplished by performing research over a range of more prolonged and continuous observation periods.

Sincerity

An example of the sincerity dimension can be seen from the case of (9) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), who delivered comments on the complete room facilities and friendly staff. In this comment, the keyword used is "complete," which means the perfection of a product or service provided by Resort (Table 5).

Table 5. Sincerity Dimension Keyword in Context

Case number	Pre-Keyword Context	Keyword	Post-Keyword Context
9	I have book a one-bedroom villa for three nights. It was an amazing experience they've showed me day by day. The room was clean. The nature ambience was good enough and super private, especially for a honeymoon couple. The room facility is quite	complete	and the staff were super friendly. If you ever gonna stay in this villa. Please just once try [REDACTED]. The massage was good and the price quite affordable. Hope you like my review. Thanks, [REDACTED]

Another example is the case of (37) (TripAdvisor Oct 2020), who recommended others to stay at the resort and have an excellent "outstanding" experience in Ubud.

Furthermore, in the case of (57) (TripAdvisor Mar 2020) said that the resort is a safe place "safe" during the Covid-19 virus pandemic that is still ongoing now because the resort has implemented Covid-19 virus prevention protocols such as providing hand sanitizer and face masks provided to visitors for free.

Furthermore, in the case of (33) (TripAdvisor Dec 2020), who conveys that the staff at the resort was accommodating by giving her advice and ensuring that visitors had the best "experienced" experience while in this place. Furthermore, another review from the case of (419) (TripAdvisor Apr 2019) said that the service provided by the resort was consistent with the keyword "consistent."

Another example is the case of (111) (TripAdvisor Feb 2020) which conveys that the staff at the resort can "be able" to do the best service to visitors and ensure that visitor requests are adequately met.

Sophistication

An example of sophistication dimension was conveyed by the case of (5) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), who conveyed that resort is a beautiful "beautiful" place, with a large clean room and comfortable. Furthermore, in the case of (7) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), (13) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), and (21) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021) also delivered reviews using the words "beautiful: or beautiful for the atmosphere of the resort environment and swimming pool.

Furthermore, the case of (35) (TripAdvisor Dec 2020) conveys that the spa facilities and services provided by the staff at the resort are good with the keyword "excellent."

Another review from the case of (123) (TripAdvisor Feb 2020) said that the resort is charming, beautiful, and luxurious with views of the surrounding greenery with the keyword "luxurious."

Another example is the case of (135) (TripAdvisor Jan 2020), who said that the resort is a quiet place and very beautiful "gorgeous." Hence, she recommends resort to other visitors.

Excitement

An example of the excitement dimension is the case of (17) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), who said that review writers feel amazingly "awesome" after staying at the resort. Another example of a case from (25) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021) says that the spa of the resort is very refreshing "refreshing." The same goes for case 27 (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), which says the pool is refreshing.

In addition, there is also a case of (47) (TripAdvisor Jun 2020) that the scenery in the resort is fantastic "breathtaking." Furthermore, from the case (157), (TripAdvisor Dec 2019) conveyed that the location, yoga facilities in the morning, and the food are excellent "crazy." The word crazy has a positive sentiment and means there is something extraordinary, excitement gained from the location, yoga in the morning, and food provided by the resort.

The case of (199) (TripAdvisor Oct 2019) said that the resort is a beautiful place and the food is well made using fresh ingredients "fresh" so this place is worth the visit. The fresh keyword is a word that has a positive sentiment and makes the spirit, novelty, and freshness of the resort.

Another example of the case (285) (TripAdvisor Aug 2019) said that this place is fantastic with friendly and helpful staff, so visitors recommend the resort for anyone who wants a unique and boutique-style stay in Ubud Bali.

Ruggedness

An example of ruggedness dimension is conveyed by the case (27) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021) that the bathroom is good with shower outside the room "outdoor." In addition, the case of (35) (TripAdvisor Dec 2020) said that they have an excellent service even though they are still in a challenging period.

Another example is (103) (TripAdvisor Feb 2020), which stated that the green atmosphere obtained while staying at the resort is the same as the sensation in the jungle.

There is also a negative sentiment within this dimension, namely from the case of (195) (TripAdvisor Oct 2019). He conveys a rather uncomfortable "uncomfortable" with a poor Wi-Fi connection that barely even works because it is slow. However, overall, he conveyed satisfaction with the services and facilities at the resort.

Another example was presented by (261) (TripAdvisor Sep 2019), who enjoyed her stay at the resort after a sunrise trip in Mount Batur, Bali. In the context of the review conveyed, this keyword has a positive sentiment because "sunrise" is a keyword related to nature, so it goes into this dimension.

Competence

The competence dimension can be explained by the example of case (1) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), which expressed gratitude for the resort staff who were very helpful "helpful" when staying at the resort.

Several other cases also conveyed helpful staff, such as the case of (3) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021). In addition, some conveyed that the staff is friendly "friendly," and this was also conveyed by the case of (7) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), who gave praise for the hospitality of the staff of resort.

Another example of this dimension is the case of (45) (TripAdvisor Aug 2020), conveying that the staff at the resort welcomed him "welcoming" well. In addition, there is also a case that conveys the case (105)(TripAdvisor Feb 2020), that the staff who are at the resort are always with a smiley face.

V. CONCLUSION

The content analysis procedure for the Resort review, which was carried out using the Provalis program, reveals that numerous aspects are important to the study's aims. Some elements, however, need to be improved in order to be more relevant to the study aims.

Furthermore, the use of the number of frequencies of words and phrases contained in the complete data set might reveal important items that form the consumer's prevailing reasoning. This prevailing reasoning explains the perceived benefits of the resort by consumers.

This approach is an option that may be used to see the brand's Top of Mind in observation. If in another study, a procedure is carried out to fill out questionnaires linked to the dimensions examined, then the test in this study is the review data already accessible on TripAdvisor.

This review is based on the opinions of customers who have purchased the exact product/service. Further investigation is carried out based on these numerous evaluations, classification based on the methodology and indicators contained in the program Provalis to generate findings that can answer the resort's Top-of-Mind reviews.

The initial step of analysis is the tabulation of word frequency, followed by the tabulation of phrase frequency, and classification that matches to the brand's keyword personality. Staff terms are most frequently expressed by datasets on TripAdvisor Reviews in word frequency tabulation. It shows a favorable feeling, and it is assumed that the resort's personnel performed admirably.

Furthermore, a case study examination of TripAdvisor evaluations for the resort from 2019 to 2021 reveals that this resort has five brand personality characteristics in this study, namely Sincerity, Sophistication, Excitement, Ruggedness, and Competence. Based on the perceptions expressed by the TripAdvisor online reviews dataset, these findings indicate the brand's personality. These results reveal the brand's personality based on the perceptions conveyed by TripAdvisor online reviews dataset.

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